

1 **Bacterial Cellulose Films Enriched with Herbal Extracts: *In Vitro* Assessment for**
2 **Wound Dressing Applications**

3 Ioana M. Bodea^{a,b}, Carmen R. Pop^c, Ancuța M. Rotar^c, Andreea Stănilă^c, Mircea C.
4 Dudescu^d, Eموke Pall^e, Giorgiana M. Cătunescu^{b,f*}

5 ^a Department of Agricultural Engineering, Polytechnic University of Cartagena, 30203
6 Cartagena, Murcia, Spain

7 ^bDepartment of Technical and Soil Sciences, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Agricultural
8 Science and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca, 400372 Cluj-Napoca, Romania

9 ^c Department of Food Science, Faculty of Food Science and Technology, University of
10 Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca, 400372 Cluj-Napoca, Romania;

11 ^dDepartment of Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, 400114 Cluj-
12 Napoca, Romania;

13 ^eDepartment of Preclinical and Clinical Sciences, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University
14 of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca, 400372 Cluj-Napoca,
15 Romania

16 ^f Food Quality & Design Group, Wageningen University & Research, Bornse Weiland 9,
17 6708, WG Wageningen, the Netherlands

18 *Corresponding author: giorgiana.catunescu@wur.nl

19 **Abstract**

20 Bacterial cellulose (BC) is a biocompatible, non-toxic wound dressing material with
21 excellent mechanical properties and moisture content. Although it lacks native antimicrobial
22 properties, its network structure allows the loading of bioactive compounds for controlled
23 release ensuring a proper environment for wound healing. In line with this, the present study
24 aimed to evaluate *in vitro* the potential use of BC loaded with two ethanolic extracts (oregano
25 and lovage) as wound dressing materials. Extracts were first tested for bioactivity, then BC
26 membranes produced by *Komagataeibacter xylinus* were characterized for thickness,
27 uniformity, and structure, being afterwards enriched with the two ethanolic extracts. The
28 enriched films were assessed for transparency, color, mechanical, antibacterial, and chemical
29 properties, being compared with the commercial BC dressing, Epicyte hydro®.
30 Cytocompatibility was evaluated *in vitro* by cell viability, adhesion, and scratch assays.
31 Overall, the present results indicate that BC films, especially when enriched with lovage
32 ethanolic extracts, offer a balance of biocompatibility, support for keratinocyte adhesion and
33 migration, showing great potential for wound-healing applications. In contrast, the enrichment
34 of BC with oregano has the advantage of enhanced antimicrobial activity but may compromise
35 the cellular interactions in the wound.

36 **Key words:** lovage; oregano; bacterial cellulose; biocompatibility; cytotoxicity; wound
37 healing

38 **1 Introduction**

39 A wound is a disruption of epithelial, anatomical, and functional integrity of a tissue;
40 thus, its restoration requires the collaboration of different cell types [1]. The healing process is
41 complex and requires multiple processes of biomolecular interactions between multiple cell
42 types, conventionally divided into four major overlapping phases: hemostasis, inflammation,
43 proliferation, and remodeling [2]. Thus, wound healing can become a challenge, as the end

44 result can be impaired, leading to altered tissue and fibrosis. Because of this, new approaches
45 are sought for wound healing management, in an attempt to meet the specific cellular needs
46 and to ensure a fast and effective tissue healing. Novel natural and synthetic biomaterials are
47 one of the current approaches that have been investigated for applications designed to improve
48 the healing process [3]. The main requirement of a biomaterial for a wound healing application
49 is its biocompatibility, which is mandatory for an appropriate host response in a healing
50 scenario [4].

51 Bacterial cellulose (BC), one of the researched biomaterials, is a natural polymer
52 produced as an extracellular polysaccharide by several *Acetobacter* bacteria. Its characteristics,
53 such as purity, biocompatibility, fibrillar structure, and mechanical properties, offer ideal
54 baseline conditions for biomedical applications, especially as a wound dressing material [5, 6].
55 Additionally, its unique nanofibrillar 3D structure promotes permeability and facilitates the
56 incorporation of active compounds while optimally releasing them, accelerating wound healing
57 [2, 7]. BC also possesses adequate adhesion, hydrophilicity, and good mechanical
58 characteristics, which offer protection to the wound environment, extending its application in
59 chronic wounds and severe burns [2]. However, BC alone does not have antibacterial
60 properties, which decreases its effectiveness as a dressing for infected wounds [8]. However,
61 antimicrobial compounds can be incorporated into BC, to broaden its applicability. Nowadays,
62 because of the increased interest in non-conventional antibacterial substances, herbal extracts
63 have become good potential agents for the enrichment of BC. They have multiple potential
64 applications in medicine due to their high content of phenolic compounds and increased
65 antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties [8-10].

66 In addition to having bioactive properties, a wound dressing based on BC also needs to
67 be biocompatible with the host tissues. Previous studies reported that BC presented a high
68 degree of biocompatibility [4, 11-13]. Although the cytocompatibility of BC has been

69 extensively studied, limited research has focused on the biocompatibility of BC enriched with
70 herbal extracts, such as oregano and lovage ethanolic extracts. The cytotoxic properties of
71 oregano extract were previously assessed on A549 human lung adenocarcinoma epithelial
72 cells, colonocytes and fibroblasts, and colon cancer Caco2 cells, or SAF-1 cells [14-16], but
73 only one study assessed the cell cytotoxicity effect of lovage ethanolic extract on hamster
74 kidney fibroblasts and HeLa (ATCC CCL-2)–cervix adenocarcinoma epithelial cells [17].
75 Moreover, the cell lines used in these studies are often not representative for skin tissue, thereby
76 limiting the relevance of the findings for wound healing applications. Furthermore, to the best
77 of our knowledge, the cytocompatibility of BC films enriched with oregano and lovage
78 ethanolic extracts has not yet been investigated within the scope of wound dressing
79 applications.

80 In this context, this study aims at assessing the *in vitro* cytocompatibility a material
81 based on BC as a matrix enriched with two herbal ethanolic extracts (oregano and lovage) as
82 bioactive compounds. This study builds upon our previous work in which BC was engineered
83 to exhibit optimal properties for use as a wound dressing material, as reported by Bodea, Beteg
84 [18]. In a subsequent study, BC was enriched with various ethanolic plant extracts, including
85 oregano and lovage, and their bioactivity was evaluated [10]. Furthermore, the extraction of
86 oregano and lovage was optimized using microwave-assisted extraction to maximize their
87 bioactive potential [9]. Thus, in the present study, we combined the previously optimized BC
88 membrane with the most bioactive oregano and lovage ethanolic extracts and subsequently
89 assessed its *in vitro* biocompatibility using a skin-relevant cell line.

90 **2 Materials and methods**

91 **2.1 Production of BC membranes**

92 Bacterial cellulose (BC) was produced by *Komagateibacter xylinus* subsp.
93 *sucrofermentans* (former name *Gluconacetobacter xylinus*) ATCC® 700178™, under static

94 aerobic conditions, following the optimized protocol by Bodea, Beteg [18]. The inoculum was
95 prepared by vortexing (MaxQ 2000) 7 to 9 colonies from a 7-day old *K. xylinus* culture in 9
96 mL sterile saline, then to 1.5×10^7 cells/mL using a spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1900),
97 at 600 nm absorbance. Five mL of the inoculum was added to 100 mL of liquid media
98 containing 50 g/L glucose, 5 g/L yeast extract, and 12.5 g/L CaCO_3 , distilled water, and
99 incubated statically at 26°C for 16 days. After fermentation, the BC pellicles were harvested,
100 washed and purified.

101 For comparison, the commercially available wound dressing Epicyte hydro® was used
102 throughout the experiments. Epicyte hydro® is a semi-transparent biomaterial made of
103 bacterial nanocellulose synthesized by *Komagataeibacter xylinus* DSM 14,666 and it is
104 primarily used as a wound dressing material [19].

105 **2.2 Thickness and uniformity of BC membranes**

106 The thickness of purified BC membranes (65 × 65 mm) was measured using a digital
107 micrometer (VTMTL557, Vinteam, 0.01-12.7 mm range). Five measurements were taken for
108 each sample, while the uniformity was determined as the standard deviation (SD) of the 5
109 measurements. All the measurements were done in triplicate, and the results were expressed as
110 mean ± SD.

111 **2.3 Structure and fiber diameter of BC membranes**

112 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to assess the structure of the nanofibers
113 of the purified BC membranes. All samples were prepared before SEM analysis by different
114 treatments in successive steps, as described by Bodea, Beteg [18]. A ZEISS EVO electronic
115 microscope was used to analyze the prepared samples. ImageJ 1.48 software was used to
116 measure the fiber diameter in 5 different image fields per sample by measuring the diameter of
117 a minimum of 100 fibers.

118 **2.4 Herb samples and ethanolic extraction**

119 Dry lovage (*Levisticum officinale*) (Stefmar Store, Râmnicu Vâlcea, Romania) and
120 oregano (*Origanum vulgare*) (Solaris, București, Romania) were used for the microwave-
121 assisted ethanolic extraction. The optimized extraction parameters reported by Bodea,
122 Cătunescu [9] were used: 49% ethanol, 160 W extracted 10 times for oregano, and 53% ethanol,
123 800 W, extracted 10 times for lovage. Briefly, 5 g of each herb were ground (5 s) and extracted
124 using a 40 mL aqueous ethanol solution (49% and 53% ethanol for oregano and lovage,
125 respectively, acidified with HCl (0.01%)), resulting in herbal ethanolic extracts with a
126 concentration of 125 mg DW/mL. After extraction, the extracts were filtered with a Büchner
127 funnel (porosity of 0.45 μm), and the volume was adjusted to 40 mL using the same ethanol
128 concentration solvent.

129 **2.5 Total phenolic content (TPC) of ethanolic extracts**

130 TPC in ethanolic extracts was determined spectrophotometrically following Folin-
131 Ciocalteu method with absorbance in the Vis domain at a wavelength λ of 750 nm (Biotek
132 multidetector UV-Vis spectrometer) [9]. A calibration curve with Gallic acid of different
133 concentrations: 1 mg /100 mL; 0.5 mg /100 mL; 0.25 mg /100 mL; 0.125 mg /mL, and 0.0625
134 mg /mL, was used to determine the TPC. The calibration curve had the following equation: y
135 = $0.9443x + 0.0608$, having an R^2 of 0.9945. The TPC was expressed in mg Gallic acid
136 equivalents (GAE)/100 g dry weight (DW) according to the calibration curve.

137 **2.6 Antioxidant activity (AA) of ethanolic extracts**

138 A modified version of 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) method was used to assess
139 the AA of the herbal extracts [9]. Samples of 250 μL ethanolic extracts were used for the
140 determinations, while 1.75 μL of DPPH and a methanol solution were used as a blank. The
141 reaction between DPPH and the antioxidants in the ethanolic extracts was determined at a
142 wavelength λ of 515 nm after 30 min. The calibration curve was plotted with Trolox using

143 various dilutions (0.5 mM/L, 0.25 Mm/L, 0.125 Mm/L, 0.00915 mM/L). The obtained curve
144 had the following equation: $y = 0.0029x + 0.0108$ and $R^2 = 0.9985$, and the AA was expressed
145 in mM Trolox equivalent (TE)/100 g DW, using the calibration curve.

146 The percentile radical-scavenging activity (I%) was computed as:

$$I\% = \frac{A_{\text{blank}} - A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{blank}}} \cdot 100, (\%) \quad (1)$$

147 where A_{blank} = absorbance of stock DPPH solution; A_{sample} = absorbance of sample.

148 **2.7 Enrichment of BC films**

149 The previously described enrichment procedure was used [10]. The purified BC and Ep
150 membranes were pressed with filter paper until almost all the liquid in their structure was
151 removed, resulting in drained BC and Ep membranes. Then, 5 discs or strips (depending on the
152 test) were placed in each test tube containing herbal extracts for 24 h, to allow the extracts to
153 load into the membranes. The enriched BC films and Ep membranes were stored in the test
154 tubes containing plant extracts at 4°C until further analysis

155 **2.8 Transparency of enriched BC films**

156 The transparency level of native BC membranes, BC films enriched with lovage (BCL)
157 or oregano (BCO) ethanolic extracts, and Epicyte hydro® (Ep) was assessed by simulations
158 [20]. Therefore, BC, BCO, BCL, and Ep were transferred to the laminated sheet of paper with
159 text typed in different colors (ROYGBIV spectrum colors). The clarity of the text underneath
160 the membranes was examined to determine if the colored text could be observed through the
161 tested BC membranes [20].

162 **2.9 Color of enriched BC films**

163 The color was measured instrumentally (3NH colorimeter) and expressed as L^* , a^* ,
164 and b^* CIELAB parameters. The chroma (C^*) and hue angle (h°), quantitative and qualitative

165 colorimetric information associated with color recognition by humans [21], together with the
166 total color difference (ΔE) were also calculated as shown in equations 2-4 [21, 22].

$$C^* = \sqrt{a^{*2} + b^{*2}} \quad (2)$$

$$h^\circ = \arctan\left(\frac{b^*}{a^*}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{\Delta L^{*2} + \Delta a^{*2} + \Delta b^{*2}} \quad (4)$$

167 where: C^* = chroma, a^* = CIELAB parameter for red-green, b^* = CIELAB parameter,
168 for yellow-blue, h° = hue angle, ΔE = total color difference, L^* = CIELAB parameter for
169 lightness.

170 Compared to the native bacterial cellulose membrane and based on the value of ΔE of
171 the enriched films, the color difference were assessed as “not noticeable” for $\Delta E \in [0-0.5)$,
172 “slightly noticeable” for $\Delta E \in [0.5-1.5)$, “noticeable” for $\Delta E \in [1.5-3.0)$, “well visible” for
173 $\Delta E \in [3.0-6.0)$, and “great difference” for $\Delta E \in [6.0- 12.0)$ [22].

174 **2.10 Mechanical properties of enriched BC films**

175 The mechanical properties of the BC membranes, BC films enriched with oregano (BCO)
176 and lovage (BCL) ethanolic extracts, and Epicyte hydro® (Ep) were evaluated using a tensile
177 testing machine (Instron 3366 (10 kN) in a tensile mode. Tests were conducted at room
178 temperature (23°C) and relative humidity of 45–50%. Samples measuring 65/20 mm were
179 stretched to failure at a constant crosshead speed (2 or 4 mm/min) [18]. For each sample, 5
180 specimens were tested, and the maximum load (N), tensile strength (MPa), elongation at break
181 (%), Young’s modulus (MPa), and stiffness (kN/cm) were calculated. Results were presented
182 as mean \pm SD of 5 measurements.

183 **2.11 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) of enriched BC films**

184 The BC membranes, BC films enriched with oregano (BCO) and lovage (BCL) ethanolic
185 extracts and Epicyte hydro® (Ep) were analyzed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy
186 (FTIR) using the Shimadzu IR Prestige -21 spectrophotometer with horizontal ATR
187 (Attenuated Total reflectance) diamond accessory with a single reflection from PIKE, using
188 ethanol as background [10]. The spectra were recorded on the wavelength range 600-3500 cm⁻¹,
189 at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, and 16 scans for one spectrum. The absorption bands characteristic of
190 the different types of bonds and functional groups (expressed in cm⁻¹) were identified. The
191 primary data obtained were processed using IR solution Software Overview (Shimadzu) and
192 OriginR 7SR1 Software (OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, USA).

193 **2.12 Antibacterial activity of ethanolic extracts and enriched BC films**

194 **2.12.1 Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC)**

195 The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined against *Escherichia coli*
196 (ATCC 25922) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 6538P) as previously described by Bodea,
197 Cătunescu [9]. Lovage and oregano ethanolic extracts (125 mg DW/mL) in 53% and 49%
198 ethanol, respectively, were tested at the following extract concentration: 59.52 mg/mL; 28.34
199 mg/mL; 13.50 mg/mL; 6.43 mg/mL; 3.06 mg/mL; 1.46 mg/mL; 0.69 mg/mL; 0.33 mg/mL;
200 0.16 mg/mL; 0.07 mg/mL; 0.04 mg/mL. Ethanol solutions (49% and 53%) were used as
201 negative controls for oregano and lovage extracts, respectively, while gentamicin (0.04 mg/mL
202 in saline solution) was used as positive control. The plates were incubated for 20-22 h at 37°C,
203 after which, 20 µL of 0.2 mg/mL resazurin aqueous solution was added to each well, followed
204 by an additional 2 h incubation at 37°C. The MIC was established as the lowest concentration
205 showing no color change (blue), indicating complete inhibition of bacterial growth. All tests
206 were performed in triplicate.

207 2.12.2 Disc-diffusion method

208

209 Standard strains of *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC
210 6538P) were prepared as previously described. The antimicrobial activity of BC membranes
211 and BC films was assessed by the disc-diffusion method, as previously described by [10], in
212 comparison with the commercial Epicyte hydro® (Ep) membranes. Both BC and Ep were cut
213 into 10 mm discs with a biopsy punch (SMI, Belgium). The obtained discs were pressed with
214 filter paper and soaked for 24 h in oregano and lovage ethanolic extracts. The BC disks
215 absorbed approximately 25 µL of 125 mg/mL extract, while the Ep discs absorbed
216 approximately 74 µL of 125 mg/mL extract. Additional BC and Ep discs were also loaded in
217 their respective ethanolic solutions (49% and 53%) and used as negative controls. BC films
218 loaded with gentamicin (0.04 mg/mL in saline solution) were used as positive controls [10].

219 2.13 *In vitro* cytocompatibility assessment

220 2.13.1 Cell viability assay

221 The MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) (Sigma-
222 Aldrich) colorimetric assay was used to determine cell viability [23]. The MTT assay is based
223 on the reduction of the yellow tetrazolium salt MTT to insoluble purple formazan crystals by
224 mitochondrial succinate dehydrogenase enzymes, which are NAD(P)H-dependent and active
225 only in metabolically viable cells. Following the reduction process, the resulting formazan
226 crystals are solubilized using dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and the absorbance is subsequently
227 measured spectrophotometrically at a wavelength of 570 nm.

228 The cell line HaCaT (CVCL_0038) was used to evaluate the cytotoxic effect of BC
229 membranes, BC films, Ep, and ethanolic extracts of oregano and lovage. The HaCaT cell line,
230 consisting of spontaneously immortalized human keratinocytes, represents a well-established
231 *in vitro* model for human epidermis and is widely used for evaluating the cytotoxicity of plant-
232 derived extracts and biomedical materials in skin-related applications [24-27].

233 Cells were cultured in propagation medium composed of Dulbecco's Modified Eagle
234 Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1% antibiotic-
235 antimycotic (AA), at a seeding density of 1×10^5 cells per well in 48-well plates, as previously
236 described by Dumitraş, Bunea [28]. The plates were incubated at 37 °C in a humidified
237 atmosphere containing 5% CO₂ and approximately 90% relative humidity. After 24 hours of
238 incubation, bacterial cellulose-based films, BC, BCO, BCL, and Ep, each measuring 30 × 30
239 mm, were introduced into the wells.

240 Additionally, the oregano and lovage ethanolic extracts were added at four different
241 concentrations: 734.85, 1498.85, 2248.15, and 2797.55 mg GAE/L for oregano extract, and
242 392.40, 784.85, 1177.30, and 1569.75 mg GAE/L for lovage extract, based on the total phenolic
243 content (TPC) determined in the ethanolic extracts. The negative control consisted of cells
244 maintained in standard propagation medium without any treatment. Cell viability was
245 evaluated after a 24-hour incubation at 37 °C. Following treatment, 0.5 mg/mL of MTT
246 solution was added to each well, and the plates were incubated further to facilitate the formation
247 of formazan crystals. Subsequently, 100 µL of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was added to each
248 well to solubilize the formazan. Absorbance was then measured at 570 nm using a
249 spectrophotometric microplate reader (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA). All experiments were
250 conducted in triplicate to ensure reproducibility.

251 The percentage of cell viability (%) was calculated based on the equation (5).

$$\text{Cell viability\%} = \frac{A_{\text{treated cells}}}{A_{\text{control cells}}} \cdot 100, (\%) \quad (5)$$

252 where A = absorbance.

253 For each tested sample, the cytotoxic activity was expressed as IC₅₀. This value
254 represents the extract concentration required to inhibit 50% of cell proliferation, and it was

255 calculated from the dose response curve, obtained using non-linear regression. All experiments
256 were performed in triplicate.

257 **2.13.2 Cell adhesion assay**

258 A cell adhesion assay was performed by placing 30 × 30 mm BC, BCO, BCL, and Ep
259 films into 24-well plates, followed by the application of 10 µL of oregano or lovage ethanolic
260 extracts, selected based on the results of the vitality test. HaCaT cells (1×10^5) were then seeded
261 onto each membrane. The oregano and lovage extracts were used at a concentration of 125 mg
262 dry weight (DW)/mL. Cell adhesion and morphology were evaluated microscopically after 3
263 and 24 hours post-seeding, as described by Roman, Şoancă [29]. The percentage of adhered
264 cells was expressed using the equation (6).

$$\text{Degree of attachment\%} = \frac{\text{No. joined cells}}{\text{Initial number}_{\text{control cells}}} \cdot 100, (\%) \quad (6)$$

265 **2.13.3 Scratch assay**

266 The migratory capacity of HaCaT cells in the presence of tested bacterial cellulose
267 membranes (BC, BCO, BCL, Ep) and herbal ethanolic extracts (oregano and lovage) was
268 assessed using the wound healing assay, commonly referred to as the scratch assay [30]. This
269 assay involves cultivating cells to form a confluent monolayer, creating a defined cell-free gap
270 (scratch) within the monolayer, and subsequently monitoring the migration of cells into this
271 area to quantify wound closure and cell motility. This technique is widely employed to evaluate
272 the effects of pharmaceutical and natural compounds on cell migration [31].

273 HaCaT cells (passage 15) were seeded in 6-well plates (6 cm diameter) and cultured
274 until reaching confluence assay [30, 32]. A linear scratch was created under sterile conditions
275 using a 200 µL pipette tip, after which detached cells were removed by refreshing the culture
276 medium. The tested membranes and ethanolic extracts were then introduced to the culture
277 wells. The control group consisted of unscratched cultures maintained under identical

278 conditions. Cell migration and wound closure were evaluated at 24 and 48 h post-scratch, with
279 calculations performed according to equations 7 and 8.

$$R_M = \frac{W_i - W_f}{t} \quad (7)$$

280 where R_M = rate of cell migration ($\mu\text{m/h}$); W_i = initial wound width (μm); W_f = final
281 wound width (μm); t = duration of migration (hour)

$$\text{Wound Closure \%} = \left(\frac{A_{t=0} - A_{t=\Delta t}}{A_{t=0}} \right) \cdot 100, (\%) \quad (8)$$

282 where $A_{t=0}$ = the initial wound width (μm); $A_{t=\Delta t}$ = wound width after n hour of the initial
283 scratch (μm).

284 **2.14 Statistical analysis**

285 XLSTAT (version 2023.1.2) and GraphPad Prism (version 10.0.0) statistical software
286 were used to analyze the data. A two-way ANOVA ($p < 0.05$) was used to compare the
287 differences among the obtained extracts and enriched bacterial cellulose membranes/films in
288 terms of the assessed parameters (physical properties and bioactivity). When ANOVA showed
289 significant differences among samples, appropriate post hoc tests were applied depending on
290 the data structure. Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) test at $p < 0.05$, Student's t-test,
291 or Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test were used to perform pairwise
292 comparisons.

293 **3 Results and discussion**

294 **3.1 Thickness and uniformity of BC membranes**

295 Purified BC membranes achieved the desired transparency and gel-like structure
296 following the two-step purification method. BC membranes had an average thickness of
297 2.19 ± 0.31 mm, consistent with previous findings, where thickness was shown to vary from

298 1.34±0.20 mm to 2.67±0.67 mm depending on fermentation period [18]. Additionally, the
299 uniformity was 0.31±0.25 mm, aligning with earlier results [18].

300 3.2 Structure and fiber diameter of BC membranes

301 BC membranes exhibited a well-organized, three-dimensional fibrillar network
302 structure, with randomly arranged nanofibers and empty spaces distributed randomly in
303 between, facilitating water absorption and retention, as shown in Figure 1. Fiber diameter
304 ranged from 7.48±0.03 to 146.94±25.12 nm, with a median of 42.53±18.66 nm. These values
305 are well in accord with previous reports, where values ranged between from 11 to 174 nm,
306 respectively [10], or from 20 nm to 173 nm reported by other authors [33]. This unique ultrafine
307 structure makes BC a promising material for the fabrication of bioactive scaffolds.

308

309

Figure 1. SEM images of the surface morphology of purified BC

310 3.3 Total phenolic content (TPC) and Antioxidant activity (AA) of ethanolic extracts

311 The total phenolic content (TPC) was significantly higher in oregano ethanolic extract,
312 almost two times higher than for lovage (Table 1). This aligns with previous studies, which
313 reported the TPC ranging from 1559.7 mg GAE/100 g DW [34] to 4314.06±81.33 mg
314 GAE/100 g DW in oregano ethanolic extracts [10]. In contrast, lovage ethanolic extracts
315 showed lower TPC values compared to oregano, but higher than in previous studies that
316 reported a range from 19.70 mg GAE/g DW [35] to 3015.25±70.02 mg GAE/100 g DW) [10].

317 The antioxidant activity (AA) of the two tested herbs mirrored the TPC, with oregano
 318 having almost 3 times higher AA than lovage (Table 1). Previous reports outlined that among
 319 other plant extracts, oregano had the highest antioxidant activity, while lovage usually
 320 exhibited a lower antioxidant activity than oregano [9, 35].

321 Table 1. Total phenolic content and antioxidant activity of oregano and lovage ethanolic
 322 extracts

Bioactivity	TPC (mg GAE/100 g DW)	AA (mM TE/100 g DW)	I (%)
Ethanolic extract			
Oregano	14987.73±12.93 ^a	105.70±0.11 ^a	37.00±1 ^a
Lovage	7848.90±15.70 ^b	37.01±0.04 ^b	14.00±1 ^b

323 Where: TPC: Total phenolic content; AA: antioxidant activity; I%: radical scavenging activity.

324 Different letters (a–b within the same column show significant differences among the samples
 325 (Fisher (LSD), $p < 0.05$).

326 3.4 Transparency of enriched BC films

327 Non-invasive wound monitoring reduces the trauma of granulating tissue, making
 328 transparent dressings highly valuable, as dressing removal can disrupt healing [20, 36]. The
 329 transparency of BC, BCO, BCL, and Ep membranes was evaluated (Figure 2). BC showed
 330 good transparency, allowing underlying text to be visible, unlike opaque Ep, which may hinder
 331 wound observation. Enriched BC films had a slight yellow tint from extracts, reducing clarity
 332 but maintaining transparency and structure. As this was a simulated test, *in vivo* validation is
 333 needed to confirm its applicability.

334 Similar to our results, the transparency of native BC membranes was previously
 335 documented [37]. Gupta, Briffa [20] showed that silver nanoparticles using curcumin-
 336 cyclodextrins (cAgNP) loaded BC hydrogels kept their transparency, and allowed the
 337 monitoring of the wound underneath, without the need of removal of the hydrogel [36].

338

339

340 Figure 2. The visual appearance by transparency test of (A) bacterial cellulose (BC) film
 341 enriched with lovage extract; (B) BC film enriched with oregano extract; (C) BC membrane;
 342 (D) Epicyte hydro®

343 3.5 Color of enriched BC films

344 The enrichment of BC was designed to obtain a wound dressing with a pleasant
 345 appearance and color and without compromising its transparency, while taking advantage of
 346 the important bioactivity of herbal extracts, mainly their antioxidant and antibacterial activity.
 347 Table 2 shows the difference among colorimetric properties of samples, which varied
 348 significantly among all color parameters ($p < 0.0001$). The chroma of the enriched membranes
 349 was significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$), being followed by BC and Ep, while the lightness
 350 parameter was significantly higher in BC ($L^* = 79.09 \pm 1.14$). The intense yellow color of BCO
 351 was confirmed by the red-green parameter and hue angle, which were significantly higher
 352 ($a^* = 1.92 \pm 0.56$; $h^\circ = 1.518 \pm 0.01$), while the yellow-blue color was significantly higher in both
 353 enriched membranes ($b^*_{BCO} = 30.17 \pm 1.75$; $b^*_{BCL} = 30.58 \pm 0.87$).

354 A significant difference was observed between the native BC and the two enriched
 355 membranes ($\Delta E_{BCO} = 26.63 \pm 2.66$; $\Delta E_{BCL} = 27.01 \pm 1.26$), while the difference between the two
 356 enriched membranes was only well visible ($\Delta E = 4.53 \pm 1.08$). The color difference between Ep

357 and BC was also significant, with a ΔE of 10.72 ± 1.09 , but still being less than half of BCO and
 358 BCL.

359 Table 2. Colorimetric properties of native BC, BC enriched with oregano and lovage extracts,
 360 and Epicyte hydro®.

	L*	a*	b*	C*	h°	ΔE (compared to native BC)
BC	79.09 \pm 1.14 ^a	-0.67 \pm 0.17 ^b	4.41 \pm 0.45 ^b	4.46 \pm 0.42 ^b	-1.42 \pm 0.05 ^c	-
BCO	73.34 \pm 2.05 ^b	1.92 \pm 0.56 ^a	30.17 \pm 1.75 ^a	30.23 \pm 1.79 ^a	1.51 \pm 0.01 ^a	26.63 \pm 2.66 ^a
BCL	72.59 \pm 1.38 ^b	-1.65 \pm 0.28 ^c	30.58 \pm 0.87 ^a	30.63 \pm 0.86 ^a	-1.52 \pm 0.01 ^d	27.01 \pm 1.26 ^a
Ep	71.23 \pm 0.96 ^c	-1.07 \pm 0.11 ^b	-2.70 \pm 0.71 ^c	2.91 \pm 0.67 ^c	1.16 \pm 0.10 ^b	10.72 \pm 1.09 ^b

361 Where: BC: bacterial cellulose, Ep: Epicyte hydro®; BCO: BC enriched with oregano extract;
 362 BCL: BC enriched with lovage extract; C*: chroma, a*: CIELAB parameter for red-green, b*:
 363 CIELAB parameter, for yellow-blue, h°: hue angle, ΔE : total color difference, L*: CIELAB
 364 parameter for lightness; Different letters (a–c within the same column show significant
 365 differences among the samples (Fisher (LSD), $p < 0.05$).

366 3.6 Mechanical properties of enriched BC films

367 The mechanical analyses showed that BC membranes supported a maximum load of
 368 3.22 ± 0.60 N and presented a tensile strength of 0.45 ± 0.03 MPa, similar to both enriched BC
 369 films (Table 3). The commercial membrane Ep, however, had significantly higher values for
 370 maximum load and stiffness ($p < 0.0001$). Ep showed significantly higher tensile strength
 371 ($p = 0.019$) and Young's Modulus ($p < 0.0001$) compared to the native BC, but similar to that of
 372 both enriched BC films. The mechanical properties of BC and enriched BC films are in
 373 agreement with previous studies [11, 18].

374 Table 3. Mechanical properties of bacterial cellulose films, compared to Epicyte hydro®

Sample	Maximum Load (N)	Tensile strength σ (MPa)	Elongation at break ϵ (%)	Young's Modulus E (MPa)	Stiffness, k (kN/cm)
BC	3.20 \pm 0.60 ^b	0.50 \pm 0.20 ^a	32.65 \pm 3.29 ^a	1.52 \pm 0.59 ^a	1.23 \pm 0.21 ^b

BCO	2.95±1.71 ^b	0.49±0.29 ^a	32.43±15.32 ^a	1.47±0.18 ^a	1.10±0.13 ^b
BCL	3.02±0.91 ^b	0.50±0.15 ^a	34.32±4.88 ^a	1.44±0.34 ^a	1.08±0.25 ^b
Ep	14.25±2.17 ^a	0.50±0.08 ^a	37.14±4.86 ^a	1.35±0.14 ^b	4.81±0.50 ^a

375 Where: BC = bacterial cellulose, EP = Epicyte hydro®; BCO = BC enriched with oregano
 376 extract; BCL = BC enriched with lovage extract; Different letters (a–d within the same column
 377 show significant differences among the samples (Fisher (LSD), $p < 0.05$).

378 **3.7 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)**

379 The Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectral analysis was used to detect functional
 380 groups of compounds present in BC, BCO and BCL ethanolic extracts, and commercially
 381 available Epicyte hydro® (Ep). According to previous studies, the ATR mode, with 16 scans
 382 per measurement, between 400 cm^{-1} and 3500 cm^{-1} was used, since BC was difficult pulverize
 383 [18, 38]. FTIR was previously used to demonstrate the presence of phenolic compounds in
 384 biofilms and to provide evidence on how the incorporation of plant extracts interacts with the
 385 chemical structure of BC [10]. It was shown that the loading of plant extracts in BC matrix
 386 does not generate many distinct spectral features that can be directly assigned to the specific
 387 molecular structures of the extract components. The FTIR major peaks of the samples and the
 388 tentative assignments of their infrared absorption bands are reported in Figure 3 and Supp.
 389 material Table 1.

390
 391 Figure 3. Comparative analysis of functional groups on bacterial cellulose (BC) membrane, BC
 392 films enriched with oregano extract (BCO), BC films enriched with lovage extract (BCO) and
 393 Epicyte hydro® (Ep).

394 The band at 3000–3352 cm^{-1} , observed in all samples, is attributed to O–H stretching
 395 vibrations in cellulose, including intra- and intermolecular hydrogen bonds, and may also arise
 396 from OH groups in alcohols, phenols, and carboxylic acids [39, 40]. In samples without extracts
 397 (BC and Ep), peaks appeared at 3325 and 3329 cm^{-1} , respectively, while a shift to 3346 cm^{-1}
 398 (BCL) and 3352 cm^{-1} (BCO) was observed, suggesting the presence of phenolic compounds.
 399 The 2978 cm^{-1} band, seen only in samples with ethanolic extracts, may arise from C–H, N–H,
 400 and O–H stretching of alkanes, amines, alcohols, or carboxylic acids [41]. Stretching vibrations
 401 of –CH, –CH₂, and –CH₃ from carbohydrates were observed in all samples, peaking at 2930
 402 cm^{-1} (BCL) and 2937 cm^{-1} (BCO). Peaks at 2926–2927 cm^{-1} in Ep and BC likely correspond
 403 to C–H stretching in aliphatic compounds and may indicate chlorophyll presence [42, 43].

404 The 2899 cm^{-1} band in BCO and BCL, shifted to 2895 cm^{-1} in BC, may reflect C–H
 405 and O–H stretching of alkenes, alcohols, and carboxylic acids, or C–C/CH₂/CH₃ stretching
 406 [38]. Bands at 1630 cm^{-1} (BCL), 1647 cm^{-1} (BCO), and 1637 cm^{-1} (BC) likely correspond to
 407 aromatic ring deformation, amino acids, flavonoids, or C=C stretching [44]. The absorption

408 bands at 1653 and 1550 cm^{-1} (amide I and II) indicate proteins, with lower intensity in BC
409 suggesting reduced protein content [45]. Weak peaks at 1516 cm^{-1} (BCO, BCL) may arise from
410 $\text{C}_{\text{ar}}=\text{C}_{\text{ar}}$ stretching in polar aromatics like phenols [46], while peaks at 1450 cm^{-1} likely reflect
411 aromatic $-\text{C}=\text{C}-$ bonds [47]. The bands at 1423–1427 cm^{-1} (BCO, BCL, BC respectively) may
412 reflect CH_2 scissoring, CH_2 symmetric stretching, or O–H in-plane bending [48-50]. Peaks at
413 1416 cm^{-1} (BCO, BCL) likely indicate terpenes (C–H) [51]. Bands at 1383–1387 cm^{-1}
414 correspond to O–H bending in alcohols and phenols [41], while peaks at 1323–1325 cm^{-1}
415 (BCL, BCO) are attributed to O–H bending in phenols [52].

416 Two absorption bands present at 1279 cm^{-1} for BCO and BCL could be attributed to
417 Ar–O in aryl ethers [53], while the bands at 1207 for BCL and 1206 for BCO, could correspond
418 to C–O stretching in ether compounds [54].

419 The absorption between 1157–1160 cm^{-1} in BC, BCO, BCL, and Ep indicates C–O–C
420 antisymmetric stretching of 1,4- β -O-glucosides [55]. Peaks at 1107 cm^{-1} (BC, BCL, BCO)
421 reflect C–C bonds in polysaccharide monomers or C–O bending [56]. Bands around 1000–
422 1100 cm^{-1} are assigned to C–O stretching in primary alcohols, C–O–C skeletal vibrations, or
423 C–O–H bending in carbohydrates [50, 56-58]. Peaks near 1040–1058 cm^{-1} (BC, BCL, BCO,
424 Ep) correspond to polysaccharide carbohydrates [59, 60]. Our spectra present weak absorption
425 between 1050 cm^{-1} (BCL) and 1058 cm^{-1} (weak for Ep) and 3 peaks at 1030 cm^{-1} , 1032 cm^{-1} ,
426 and 1034 cm^{-1} for BC, BCL, and BCO, respectively.

427 The weak 1080 cm^{-1} band in BCL and BCO may reflect $\text{C}_{\text{sp}^3}\text{--OH}$ vibrations in
428 alcohols or carboxylic acids and $\text{C}_{\text{sp}^3}\text{--O}$ in esters [61]. A strong peak at 1003 cm^{-1} in BC
429 arises from C3–O3 stretching, key for cross-linking [62]. Bands at 900–700 cm^{-1} correspond
430 to out-of-plane deformation of substituted phenolics, polar compounds, and $-(\text{CH}_2)_n$ - rocking
431 [46, 63]

432 Weak bands at 896 cm^{-1} (BC) and 899 cm^{-1} (BCL, BCO) correspond to $\nu(\text{C-O-C})$
 433 vibrations of β -glycosidic bonds in (1,4)- β -D-cellulose, reflecting antisymmetric out-of-phase
 434 ring stretching between glucose units [64, 65].

435 3.8 Antibacterial activity of ethanolic extracts and enriched BC films

436 The results of the MIC of ethanolic extracts showed that both oregano and lovage
 437 extracts had lower activity against *E. coli*, while against *S. aureus*, oregano had significantly
 438 higher activity than lovage (Table 4). Gentamicin had the highest antibacterial activity against
 439 both tested strains, significantly different than the two extracts, showing the positive control
 440 validation of the test. Previous reports showed that oregano had a significantly higher activity
 441 against both *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, compared to lovage [9].

442 The disc-diffusion test of the ethanolic extracts showed that oregano had significantly
 443 higher antibacterial activity ($p < 0.0001$) against *S. aureus*, compared to gentamicin (0.04
 444 mg/mL), while lovage had no antibacterial activity (Table 4). Meanwhile, *E. coli* was resistant
 445 to both ethanolic extracts, and only gentamicin had a significant effect ($p = 0.001$; 3.67 ± 1.53
 446 mm). Bodea, Catunescu [10] reported that oregano extract had antibacterial activity against *S.*
 447 *aureus* (1.50 ± 0.71 mm), while being more active against *E. coli* (3.00 ± 1.41 mm), but still lower
 448 than rosemary.

449 Table 4. Antimicrobial activity assessed by disc diffusion method and minimum inhibitory
 450 concentration (MIC) of ethanolic extracts, bacterial cellulose (BC) and Epicyte hydro®
 451 enriched with oregano and lovage extracts against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

Sample	Disc diffusion method		Minimum inhibitory concentration	
	DIZ <i>S. aureus</i> (mm)	DIZ <i>E. coli</i> (mm)	MIC <i>S. aureus</i> (mg/mL)	MIC <i>E. coli</i> (mg/mL)
O	8.33 ± 1.04^{cd}	R ^e	0.69	28.34
L	R ^g	R ^e	28.34	28.34
C ⁺	5.00 ± 2.65^e	3.67 ± 1.53^c	0.04	0.04
BC	R ^g	R ^e	NA	NA
BCO	7.33 ± 0.58^d	R ^e	NA	NA
BCL	R ^g	R ^e	NA	NA

BCC⁺	10.33±1.15 ^{ab}	5.00±0.00 ^b	NA	NA
Ep	2.33±0.58 ^f	2.16±0.76 ^d	NA	NA
EpO	9.33±0.58 ^{bc}	R ^e	NA	NA
EpL	R ^e	R ^e	NA	NA
EpC⁺	11.33±0.58 ^a	7.17±0.76 ^a	NA	NA

452 Where: DIZ: diameter of inhibition zone; O: oregano extract; L: lovage extract; C⁺:
 453 Gentamicin (0.04 mg/mL); BC: bacterial cellulose; BCO: BC enriched with oregano extract;
 454 BCL: BC enriched with lovage extract; BCC⁺= BC enriched with gentamicin 0.04 mg/mL; EP:
 455 Epicyte hydro®: EpO: Ep enriched with oregano extract; EpL: Ep enriched with lovage extract;
 456 EpC⁺: Ep enriched with gentamicin 0.04 mg/mL; NA – not applicable; Different letters (a–g
 457 within the same column show significant differences among the samples (Fisher (LSD), p <
 458 0.05).

459 Epicyte hydro® films showed significantly higher antibacterial activity than BC films
 460 (p<0.0001) against both strains (Table 4). The lower activity of enriched BC is likely due to
 461 the smaller extract volume loaded (26 µL vs. 75 µL). As previously reported, native BC had no
 462 effect against *S. aureus* or *E. coli* [10]. Among the two tested BC films, only BCO showed
 463 activity against *S. aureus* (7.33±0.58 mm), being lower than gentamicin (10.33±1.15 mm). *E.*
 464 *coli* was resistant to both BC films except for gentamicin loaded BC (5.00±0.00 mm). Previous
 465 reports showed that BC enriched with oregano ethanolic extract had a lower antibacterial
 466 activity against *S. aureus* (1.15±0.5 mm) compared to BC loaded with lovage (2.15±0.5 mm),
 467 while *E. coli* was resistant to the activity of both extracts [10].

468 Epicyte hydro® (Ep) films showed significant differences in antimicrobial activity
 469 (p<0.0001), with the gentamicin loaded films being the most effective against both tested
 470 strains (Table 4). Native Ep exhibited modest activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, consistent
 471 with previous reports [66], despite the manufacturer providing no details about any additional
 472 active compounds in its formulation. The enrichment with oregano extract increased the
 473 antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (9.33±0.58 mm) but not *E. coli*, while lovage displayed

474 no effect. The reduced activity compared to native Ep may result from removing the original
475 liquid during sample preparation. Previous studies showed that the Epicyte hydro® dressing
476 has antibacterial activity, as after a 24 h treatment it displayed a statistically significant (2.0
477 log) reduction of *S. aureus* bacterial density ($p = 0.0055$) [66].

478 **3.9 *In vitro* cytocompatibility analysis**

479 **3.9.1 Cell viability assay**

480 Oregano and lovage ethanolic extracts did not exhibit cytotoxic effects at the tested
481 concentrations (734.85, 1498.85, 2248.15, and 2797.55 mg GAE/L for the oregano extract, and
482 392.40, 784.85, 1177.30, and 1569.75 mg GAE/L for the lovage extract), based on the TPC
483 content determined in the extracts (Figure 4). BCO and BCL induced a significant reduction in
484 cell proliferation compared to the control BC and Ep (Figure 4). In contrast, the Ep and BC
485 membranes showed a positive effect on cell viability, with average values of 102.91% and
486 107.18%, respectively. Notably, the BC membranes exhibited higher proliferation rates
487 compared to the commercial Ep, which may be explained by several inherent structural and
488 physicochemical characteristics of BC. BC possesses a highly pure, nanofibrous 3D
489 architecture with interconnected nanofiber and elevated water-holding capacity, which together
490 generate a hydrated, biomimetic microenvironment that facilitates cell attachment, nutrient
491 transport, and waste diffusion [67]. Moreover, the nanofibrillar surface and mechanical
492 strength of BC resemble those of the extracellular matrix, promoting enhanced cell spreading
493 and proliferation [68]. The similarity of BC to the natural extracellular matrix, along with its
494 excellent biocompatibility and lack of cytotoxicity, explains the observed increased cell
495 viability [69]. These properties make BC a strong candidate for use as a scaffold in tissue
496 engineering and cell culture systems [70].

497

498 Figure 4. Cell viability assay of oregano and lovage ethanolic extracts and bacterial cellulose
 499 (BC) membrane, BC films enriched with oregano extract (BCO), BC films enriched with
 500 lovage extract (BCO), and Epicyte hydro® (Ep). The volumes of extracts used in the trials
 501 correspond to the total polyphenolic content (TPC) in the wells of 734.85, 1498.85, 2248.15,
 502 and 2797.55 mg GAE/L for oregano extract, and 392.40, 784.85, 1177.30, and 1569.75 mg
 503 GAE/L for lovage extract, respectively. C – negative control; different lowercase letters (a–c)
 504 show significant differences among the samples (Fisher (LSD), $p < 0.05$); * shows a
 505 significance at a level of $p < 0.05$ (t-test)

506 In wound healing assays, using HaCaT keratinocytes, cell viability above 100%
 507 indicates cytocompatibility and pro-regenerative potential, reflecting not only non-toxicity but
 508 also enhanced cell proliferation or metabolic activity which are crucial during the re-
 509 epithelialization phase of wound healing [71, 72].

510 Previous studies confirm the biocompatibility of BC, showing high viability in L929
 511 fibroblasts (121.9% initially, while 73.6% after 72 h) and over 90% viability in keratinocytes,
 512 with no cytotoxic effects on 3T3 fibroblasts, supporting its use in wound dressings [4, 12, 13].
 513 Oregano ethanolic extracts showed a dose dependent cytotoxicity: in A549 cells, viability
 514 decreased with an LC50 of 14 µg/mL, while in Caco2 cells, about 30% reduction was observed
 515 at 300 µg/mL. Normal fibroblasts were affected only at high doses (500 µg/mL), indicating

516 some selectivity [14, 15]. Data on lovage are limited, but studies on *Mutellina purpurea* (Alpine
 517 lovage) extracts showed cell-dependent effects, with higher sensitivity in BHK-21 fibroblasts
 518 than HeLa cells [17].

519 3.9.2 Cell adhesion assay

520 Three hours after cell seeding onto the films and the standard culture surface in multi-
 521 compartment plates, oregano extract exhibited a reduced cell attachment rate of 53.56%,
 522 compared to 87.21% in the untreated control (Figure 5). In contrast, lovage extract promoted a
 523 higher degree of cell attachment, reaching 76.6%.

524
 525 Figure 5. Cell adhesion assay of oregano and lovage ethanolic extracts and bacterial cellulose
 526 (BC) membrane, BC films enriched with oregano extract (BCO), BC films enriched with
 527 lovage extract (BCL), and Epicyte hydro® (Ep). O – oregano ethanolic extract; L- lovage
 528 ethanolic extract; C – negative control; Different lowercase letters (a–e show significant
 529 differences among the samples (Tukey's multiple comparisons test, $p < 0.05$).

530 Among the cellulose-based films, the attachment rates varied from 57.65% for BCO to
 531 79.32% for the Ep membrane. The BCL and BC membranes showed intermediate values of
 532 68.9% and 75.89%, respectively. After 24 hours, all samples exhibited a significant increase in
 533 cell attachment. The highest levels were recorded for BC and Ep membranes, with 98.3% and
 534 97.32%, respectively. BCL showed a slightly lower attachment rate (95.8%), while BCO
 535 exhibited the lowest (79.79%). These results suggest that BC films, particularly those enriched

536 with lovage extract, support effective cell adhesion and may represent biocompatible and safe
537 materials for potential applications in wound healing.

538 Qiu, Qiu [4] assessed the behavior of mouse skin fibroblast cells (L929) cells in contact
539 with BC membranes by SEM and fluorescent inverted microscope. Cell attachment studies
540 demonstrated that BC membranes had no cytotoxicity and could be a good carrier for cell
541 growth [4]. Similar, Lin, Lien [11] observed that L929 cells attached on BC membranes which
542 revealed cytocompatibility. Fu, Zhou [13] also confirmed the biocompatibility of BC
543 membranes, as they had no toxic effects on the survival of mouse embryonic fibroblasts (3T3
544 line) cultured on the surface of BC, this being beneficial for cells' attachment and proliferation.
545 Nwe, Furuike [73] reported that that the percent of attached NIH/3T3 cells on BC membranes
546 was found to be higher than 70%, which suggest that NIH/3T3 cells could attach well on BC
547 membranes.

548 **3.9.3 Scratch assay**

549 The results of the scratch wound healing assay showed distinct differences in HaCaT
550 cell migration after 24 and 48 hours of treatment (Figures 6 and 7). The cells exposed to BC
551 and EP exhibited significant wound closure (Figures 6 b; 7), pointing to their capacity to
552 facilitate keratinocyte movement and regeneration. The almost complete closure seen with BC
553 is consistent with its biocompatibility, creating a supportive environment for cell proliferation
554 and migration. The film enriched with lovage extract (BCL) also promoted cell migration
555 (Figures 6 a; 7), but to a lower extent than BC and EP. This suggests that lovage extract may
556 provide additional bioactivity, potentially through polyphenolic compounds with antioxidant
557 and anti-inflammatory effects that enhance the healing process [74]. In contrast, adding
558 oregano extract to BC led to a significant decrease level of migration. This may be attributed
559 to the stronger antimicrobial profile of oregano, which at certain concentrations could exert a
560 mildly inhibitory or cytostatic influence on cellular activity [14].

561 When tested independently, the lovage extract supported higher cell motility than the
 562 oregano extract (Figures 6 a; 7), aligning with earlier adhesion data. These findings imply that
 563 lovage extract may be more conducive to promoting wound healing in this *in vitro* model,
 564 possibly due to a more balanced biological activity that preserves cell health while encouraging
 565 migration [75, 76]. Orlando, Basnett [12] assessed the wound healing process, by the scratch
 566 assay, by using immortalized keratinocyte cells in the presence of the BC. The wound margins
 567 were observed over 7 days until complete coverage of the scratch, and the results showed an
 568 almost complete closure after 5 days. The presence of BC did not inhibit cell migration to the
 569 wound area, and the recovery rate was similar to the control, i.e., keratinocytes in growth
 570 medium only. After 2 days, the scratched area started to be covered with keratinocytes, proving
 571 that the cells were alive and active from both migratory and proliferative points of view. BC
 572 determined a wound closure of 100% at day 7

573
 574 Figure 6. Cell migration rate (a) and wound closure (b) in the scratch assays of oregano and
 575 lovage ethanolic extracts and bacterial cellulose (BC) membrane, BC films enriched with
 576 oregano extract (BCO), BC films enriched with lovage extract (BCO), and Epicyte hydro®

577 (Ep). O – oregano ethanolic extract; L- lovage ethanolic extract; C – negative control; Different
578 lowercase letters (a–e show significant differences among the samples (Tukey's multiple
579 comparisons test, $p < 0.05$).

580
581 Figure 7. Scratch wound healing assay: HaCaT cell migration after 48 hours of exposure to
582 oregano and lovage ethanolic extracts, bacterial cellulose (BC), BC-based composite
583 membranes, and Epicyte Hydro®. Treatments included BC, BC enriched with oregano extract
584 (BCO), BC enriched with lovage extract (BCL), oregano ethanolic extract (O), lovage ethanolic
585 extract (L), and Epicyte Hydro® (EP). BC: bacterial cellulose; BCO: BC + oregano extract;
586 BCL: BC + lovage extract; O: oregano ethanolic extract; L: lovage ethanolic extract; EP:
587 Epicyte Hydro®.

588 4 Conclusion

589 Oregano ethanolic extract had overall higher bioactivity compared to lovage across all
590 measured parameters, exhibiting nearly double the total content of polyphenols and almost
591 three times higher antioxidant activity. Additionally, oregano extract exhibited the highest
592 antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, compared to lovage and gentamicin in the disc-diffusion
593 test, while both extracts were ineffective against *E. coli*. Among the tested films, Epicyte

594 hydro® showed significantly higher antibacterial activity compared to the enriched BC films,
595 while native BC exhibited no antibacterial effect. BC loaded with oregano showed moderate
596 activity against *S. aureus*, while both BCO and BCL displayed no effect against *E. coli*.

597 BC films enriched with oregano or lovage extracts exhibited good biocompatibility and
598 wound-healing properties. Although BCO displayed overall higher antimicrobial effects, it
599 significantly inhibited the initial cell proliferation, adhesion (79.79%), and keratinocyte
600 migration, likely due to its more intense bioactivity. In contrast, BCL showed a bioactivity
601 lower than BCO, however exhibiting high cell viability (91%) and cell attachment (95.8%),
602 with enhanced wound closure (66%), but lower than native BC and Epicyte® (Ep) membranes
603 (98.3% and 97.32%, respectively). Both BC and Ep membranes enhanced the cell viability
604 (107.1% and 102.9% respectively), most likely due to their hydrogel-like, nanofibrous structure
605 of BC that promotes cell attachment and nutrient exchange. Additionally, the scratch
606 wound-healing assays showed that BC and Ep membranes facilitated nearly complete HaCaT
607 cell migration over 48 hours, followed closely by BCL, while BCO exhibited slower wound
608 closure. Overall, these results indicate that BC films, especially when enriched with lovage
609 ethanolic extracts, offer a balance of biocompatibility, support for keratinocyte adhesion and
610 migration, showing great potential for wound-healing applications. In contrast, the enrichment
611 with oregano offers enhanced antimicrobial activity but may involve slight compromises in
612 cellular interactions.

613 Current findings are highly promising, especially regarding the biocompatibility of the
614 lovage-enriched BC films. Still, further research is needed to fully establish their effectiveness
615 in biomedical applications. In particular, *in vivo* studies are essential to evaluate their
616 biocompatibility, potential, safety, and overall performance in the complex biological
617 environment of wound healing. Such investigations will provide critical insights into their
618 clinical relevance and support the development of new, effective bioactive wound dressings.

619 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

620 **Ioana M. Bodea:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing-Original draft
621 preparation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Carmen R. Pop:** Methodology, Investigation.
622 **Ancuța M. Rotar:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing. **Andreea**
623 **Stănilă:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing- Original draft preparation. **Mircea C. Dudescu:**
624 Methodology, Investigation. **Emoke Pall:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing- Original draft
625 preparation. **Giorgiana M. Cătunescu:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal
626 analysis, Validation, Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing.

627 **Declaration of competing interest**

628 The authors declare that they have no known competing interests that could have appeared to
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634 **Data Availability**

635 The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo repository at:
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